

D-A CANs: Diels-Alder epoxies and their fibre-reinforced polymer composites

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Introduction

- Covalent adaptable networks (CANs) are a class of network polymers which bridge the gap between thermosets and thermoplastics¹
- These materials make use of dynamic chemistry in their crosslinks to impart added functionality such as repairability (self-healing),² reshapeability² and recyclability³
- The Diels-Alder (DA) reaction is one of the most widely-researched reactions⁴ in modern chemistry: the [4+2] cycloaddition/cycloreversion of an e-rich diene and an e-poor dienophile
- In this project we have modified DGEBA epoxy resin (EPON™ 828) and crosslinked it with bismaleimides to create thermally-activated CANs
- We then characterise these DA-epoxy CANs and apply them to create functional fibre-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs)

CAN chemistry

Figure 1. The mechanism of CAN healing: decrosslinking and flow.

The (retro) Diels-Alder reaction occurring at the crosslinks between the furan and bismaleimide units of the modified epoxy.

Processing & thermal behaviour

Figure 3. Differential scanning calorimetry of cbe08.

Figure 4. Dynamic mechanical analysis of cbe08.

Figure 5. Cyclic rheological profile of cbe08.

Polymer mechanical performance

Figure 6. 3-point-bending flexural (tangent) moduli ± 1 standard deviation.

Figure 7. 3-point-bending flexural strengths (white) and failure strain (red) ± 1 standard deviation.

- Flexural moduli of the DA epoxies approximates unmodified DGEBA-based control systems
- Strength and failure strain are significantly lower the control systems
- Stress-strain curves are linear-elastic to failure: very brittle
- Currently attributing this behaviour to high crosslink density and significant prepolymer crystallinity

Figure 8. Representative 3-point-bend stress-strain curves of cbe08 (white) and cbe10 (red) DA epoxy polymers.

Composite healing & recycling

Figure 9. Above, cbe08 crossply GFRP specimens after flexural testing. Below, the same specimens after hot-pressing (1 tonne, 135 °C, 180 s).

Figure 10. Representative 3-point-bend stress-strain curves of a cbe08 GFRP (8-ply crossply).

Figure 11. Percentage healing efficiency (simple) and percentage damage in terms of tangent flexural modulus.

Note, increase in stiffness beyond 100% recovery is attributed to increase in V_f .

Figure 12. DA-epoxy GFRP recycling via DCM gelation. Fibres top, resin bottom.